

BUSINESS DEFINITION - FINDINGS MATRIX

Market Practices	Composite Activities	Designable Elements	Underlying Single Activities	Consequences	Illustrative Quotes from In-depth Interviews (Sayings)	Excerpts from Unobtrusive Observation and Document Analysis (Doings)		
Depicting the market shaping (NENONEN; STORBACKA, 2018a)	Business Definition (Position report)	Bitcoin as a first gateway for entry	Riding from the wild west	Demonstrates the unique role of bitcoin as a trigger to the development of novel business models	<p>"I bought a small portion of bitcoin at [omitted] and sent it to my wallet on my cellphone, and this experience was enjoyable. So the use of technology, I said, is going to be revolutionary." (P16)</p> <p>"Before that, I started attending several events on blockchain and found out that I had some friends who were 'desperate' for bitcoin. I did not even know they invested, and there was also another group within the bank that I ended up discovering that had a group that already liked this subject." (P3)</p> <p>"So, in 2016 I had my first experience registering in the [omitted], buying one hundred reais, just a fraction of bitcoin, so that was my first experience." (P10)</p> <p>"But even so, what I feel is that it is a big wild west, it is a fucking wild west in every way." (P8)</p> <p>"When I entered this world, it was 'fuck the banks', total anarchy, 'the dollar will end'... You know, much nonsense. But then I looked like this, I said, man, this here, as my company's partner likes to say, the genius is out of the bottle, the genie came out of the bottle, there is no way to hold it. And then the establishment realized that. And what is the establishment? Then I divide it into two parts: governments and corporations." (P15)</p> <p>"[...] several very serious institutions started paying attention to crypto and launching initiatives, several household names in addition to Fidelity, right... What crowned recently a few weeks ago was PayPal opening access to crypto investment for all Americans." (P14)</p>	<p>In an interview with members of YouTube channel specialized in cryptocurrencies, P7 has mentioned his first experience with Bitcoin and how it triggered him to believe in the potential cryptocurrencies, including perceiving the need in which grounded the Firm B value proposition (content extracted from a YouTube video).</p>		
					Unfolding business opportunities	Discloses that, in spite of new, the market presents several business opportunities	<p>"[...] I entered this only as a gateway to understand the technology and see potential and see that cryptoassets is much bigger than cryptocurrencies. And in fact, it is another business, it is another business." (P5)</p> <p>"Bearing in mind that the downward trend in the Selic rate continues, weakening of the local currency, so any product that offers, for example, 3% in the dollar is something surreal already within the market." (P11)</p> <p>"[...] this blockchain market is still at a period in which competition is very low and has more collaboration than competition because it is one of the new markets." (P1)</p> <p>"So, I understand that we have a very pioneering role in the beginning. Oh man, this is cool, let us do it. We run, run, run, and do it. Until today we work like that, me and our CTO, mainly [...] We are kind of creating a niche that did not exist." (P7)</p> <p>"So our goal is to continue growing and influencing the market." (P9)</p> <p>"We want to place ourselves as a leader in this, so, both in terms of access by traditional investors, and the ones who are not specialized nerds who know how to operate a crypto portfolio, who will be able to buy safely, not fall into a pyramid, and such. We want to be that main alternative, whatever the way, today the exposure via a fund, tomorrow things can change, suddenly there will be smart contracts in the middle, we want to be part of this application." (P13)</p>	<p>Similar to Firm D, Firm E has been also periodically publishing a market report on its website. In addition to the performance evaluation, the portfolio manager writes these reports by reverberating announcements of relevant players in the market and opportunities that they have been tackling (content extracted from Firm E website).</p> <p>On their Instagram, Firm D frequently celebrates the rentability achieved by their funds when compared to the competitors. This result is given by an external actor that investigates the performance of all funds in Brazil and verifies those who obtained the best returns. This position strengthens the leadership position achieved by Firm D (content extracted from Firm D Instagram).</p>
					Trailblazing the road	Suggests the company's vision as a market shaper	Illustrates the market journey of maturity through emblematic episodes	Illustrates the market journey of maturity through emblematic episodes

Representational Practices

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Making sense of the market directions (NENONEN; STORBACKA, 2018a)		Business Definition (Directions)	Empowering a sustainable and social agenda	Catalyzes groundbreaking strategies to deliver social value	<p>"So I think you have a maturing of the financial market that I think happens on a global level, with capitals that are more patient capitals, capitals that are so interested in investing in things with purpose... There is this ESG agenda, you know, environmental, social, and governance. And I think it is interesting that in the order of these letters, the environmental agenda in the financial world happen first." (P6)</p> <p>"I would say that this environmental agenda, I think it is the one that has the most potential for use because I think it is the one that is growing the most in the world in terms of the volume of resources to be invested." (P1)</p> <p>"The underdeveloped countries are running faster after adopting cryptocurrency alternatives as an economic model, and this is a worldwide movement, a pity that few people read about it are interested in Brazil, I suppose, still due to the negative issue of the history of cryptocurrencies, that there must be a palliative deconstruction [...]". (P17)</p> <p>"Then I think that may be a market for a product like this, as a transparent investment or maybe we can give value to transparency, monetize transparency in some way. And maybe cryptocurrencies is a vehicle for that; if we can marry the design of technology as a regulatory design that favors an arrangement like this". (P6)</p> <p>"I give you a smart contract that you do not need to see the other smart contracts. Just look at that one. That is different. So I do not even need to audit smart contracts anymore. I just need to audit only one, and all the other derivatives have the characteristics of confidence from the one whose it is indicating." (P3)</p> <p>"I...J bringing the government closer to a DAO, not a DAO at all, but some things, mainly in the trust." (P3)</p> <p>"I...J a token as a service, a token from us, from which you could derive other tokens in such a way that yourself without knowing the specific token's smart contract, you know a priori, by the generic token that that specific token follows, the minimum transparency rules." (P3)</p> <p>"I...J We are an ecosystem of cryptocurrencies, and our vein is the intelligence to understand what the consumer needs and what we believe in most is tokenization. Because I think what will remain after this fever everything is tokenization. Because tokenization is the ability to bring a behavior, a good, an asset, a physical right to a digital environment." (P11)</p> <p>"I think there will be a B3 Crypto, a crypto stock exchange for tokenized assets. I imagine our firm as a complete bank offering a complete multi-cryptocurrency bank, offering a total crypto home broker, offering a complete crypto investment menu along with the investment traditional financial system, like a very well integrated thing." (P8)</p> <p>"I...J if you ask, choose something that can make this Tokenomics groundbreak in Brazil? It is to have some regulation that defines what the token is and what regulations are about the token." (P1)</p> <p>"To be able to make this possible in the world from a regulatory point of view, and also from a pure infrastructure point of view, there are challenges. We have to work with governments and partners in several countries for this to happen, not only in Brazil but in the United States, Bermuda, Cayman, and wherever else we dream of." (P14)</p> <p>"I...J how do we articulate with these government entities not only to promote applications and use technology to solve their problem but mainly how all these solutions will be integrated in the future because they will have to talk." (P6)</p>	<p>Firm F has been conceiving different tokens to promote a fairer and more impactful economy, linking investors directly to impactful entrepreneurs. Through the financial activities in their blockchain payment service, investors could earn tokens for further support projects aligned to sustainable development goals (content extracted from Firm F website and Instagram)</p> <p>Members of Firm A have been fostering cooperation with several development banks. This initiative collaborates to increase the potential and organize the blockchain ecosystem on a worldwide scale (content extracted from a public interview of P1 to a news media website and a presentation file ministered by P3 in a public innovation event).</p> <p>Members of Firm D and Firm E were invited to discuss the cryptoassets industries in a YouTube live. In an unanimous position, they suggested that stocks will be tokenized in the future given the gain of productivity (context extracted from a news media website and a YouTube video).</p> <p>A C-level member of Firm F has pioneered the public debate with the national congress of Brazil. In a public audience, they discussed the challenges of a possible regulatory framework and the relevance of government support towards entrepreneurship in this sector (extracted from Brazilian national congress website).</p>
			Scaling the transparency	Sparks a novel way to deliver transparency to the society	<p>"I...J We are an ecosystem of cryptocurrencies, and our vein is the intelligence to understand what the consumer needs and what we believe in most is tokenization. Because I think what will remain after this fever everything is tokenization. Because tokenization is the ability to bring a behavior, a good, an asset, a physical right to a digital environment." (P11)</p> <p>"I think there will be a B3 Crypto, a crypto stock exchange for tokenized assets. I imagine our firm as a complete bank offering a complete multi-cryptocurrency bank, offering a total crypto home broker, offering a complete crypto investment menu along with the investment traditional financial system, like a very well integrated thing." (P8)</p> <p>"I...J if you ask, choose something that can make this Tokenomics groundbreak in Brazil? It is to have some regulation that defines what the token is and what regulations are about the token." (P1)</p> <p>"To be able to make this possible in the world from a regulatory point of view, and also from a pure infrastructure point of view, there are challenges. We have to work with governments and partners in several countries for this to happen, not only in Brazil but in the United States, Bermuda, Cayman, and wherever else we dream of." (P14)</p> <p>"I...J how do we articulate with these government entities not only to promote applications and use technology to solve their problem but mainly how all these solutions will be integrated in the future because they will have to talk." (P6)</p>	
			Setting regulatory expectations	Defines important steps that are expected to advance the market		

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References

NENONEN, S.; STORBACKA, K. Smash: Using market shaping to design new strategies for innovation. Value Creation, and Growth, 2018.